

EXAMINING THE ADMINISTRATOR'S INTERPERSONAL SKILLS OF LUUK NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL, MBHTE, BARM, PHILIPPINES: BASIS FOR HUMAN RELATIONSHIP TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT

Abuzamier A. Asanji¹, Nagder J. Abdurahman¹, Norman A. Abdurahman¹, Alden T. Taradji¹, Nuralyn Asmadi¹, Abubakar J. Radjuni¹, Fatima Shaira J. Balla¹, Mohammad Sharief S. Amlih¹, Raquel Aidarus²

¹*Mindanao State University-Sulu, Capitol Site, Jolo, Sulu, Philippines*

²*Luuk National High School, MBHTE-Sulu, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11120542>

ABSTRACT

In the school context, teaching personnel is considered to be the object and subject of educational development. Administrators need to possess some kind of skills if only to manage its human resource effectively. Hence, this paper aimed to explore the school administrators' interpersonal of Luuk National High School. The school administrators include the school principal, head teachers, and all department heads of the said school. A descriptive survey method was used, and a self-device questionnaire was the main instrument of this investigation. Meanwhile, both descriptive and inferential statistics such as frequency and percentage, t-test, and one-way ANOVA were used in the treatment of data. It was found that majority of the teachers in Luuk NHS were male; 28- 35 years old, with 16 years and above teaching experience; and with baccalaureate degree; The school administrator's interpersonal were rated strongly agreed which means they have exhibited these skills to a high extent. Furthermore, there was a significant difference found on the perception of teachers on administrator's interpersonal skills in terms of age and educational qualification; While there is no significant difference on the same skills according gender and length of service.

Keywords: *administrators, interpersonal skills, human relations, development, administrative skills, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Mastering the art of navigation towards the achievement of the school vision is one of the key elements of an effective school administrator. In a school setting, the ability to understand, communicate, and influence people along the process is vital. (Jupakkal M., et al., 2024; Isa J, Madjid J., et al., 2024 & A. Abdurahman, 2023). Since, people are considered to be the life and death of the organization, it is utmost necessary for school managers to develop their interpersonal skills in order to deal with routinely interaction with teachers in the workplace.

Adeniyi and Omoteso, (2014) posited that good interpersonal interaction of school administration and teachers has positive effect academic achievement and school climate as a whole. Good interpersonal interaction with teachers and parents can lead to positive effect on academic achievement. Kanthasamy (2019) also affirmed that there was a positive relationship between interpersonal skills and workers' performance. Furthermore, Peretomode (2006) argued that human relation is not just harmonizing people in the work place but influencing them to work cohesively in the context of school goals.

Further, most school managers today often neglect upgrading their skills in the art of dealing with people. They failed to realize that interpersonal competence is equally important with other managerial skills such as administrative and technical skills. Nworah (2020) observed that some school heads hoard vital information from staff and use unclear statements in delegating tasks. The result is role ambiguity and role conflict that hinder school administration.

School like Luuk National High School must be led by school manager that addresses human side of the enterprise to response to changing demands of times in the local, national, and international academic community. It is with these aforementioned views that moved these researchers to study on the interpersonal of the school administrators of same. It is believed that this investigation has the potential benefits to all school administrators of the entire Division of Sulu under the Ministry of Basic, technical and Higher Education, Southern Philippines.

Research Questions

The overall purpose of the study was to determine the level of interpersonal skills of the school administrator as manifested in Luuk National High School, Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim, Mindanao, Philippines. Specifically, this paper seeks to find answer to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender, age, length of service and educational qualification?
2. What is the extent of interpersonal skills manifested by the school administrators at Luuk National High School as perceived by secondary school teachers?

3. Is there significant difference on the perception of secondary school teachers on the interpersonal skills of the school administrators when the data are grouped according to their demographic profile?

METHODOLOGY

This section tackles the research methodology in the study, This includes the research locale; research respondents, instrumentation, data collection techniques, statistical tool used; and the scope and delimitation of the study.

Research Locale

The setting of the study was at Luuk National High school located at the eastern hemisphere of the Province of Sulu. Said school belongs to the second congressional legislative district approximately 60-kilometer to the capital town of the province-municipality of Jolo. Luuk national NHS has been continuously serving thousands of students every year ranging from junior to senior high school department I. It is currently managed by a school principal with more than twenty faculty members from two departments. The researchers choose this school as setting of the study because of the following reasons: first, it has greater accessibility considering that the researchers is currently connected at the said school. second, the researchers feels that there is a need for the school administrator' to be given feedback on their performance for them to reflect and learn. Third, this research work will hope to give insights to the administrators and teachers in order to improve the entire school climate.

Research Respondents

The researchers used a total enumeration in the selection of the respondents. It means that all 30 faculty members of Luuk NHS including Junior and Senior High School were taken as respondents of the study. These respondents answered the self-made questionnaire after being validated by the panel members or experts. They were the ones that determine the level of Interpersonal and supervisory skills manifested by the school administrators.

Instrumentation

After a thorough library works of the review of related literatures and studies, the researcher s finally came up with a self-made questionnaire and validated by the panel members or experts.

According to Padua (2001) in Cristobal Jr & Cristobal (2013) that questionnaire is a list of planned, written questions related to a particular topic with a space provided for the response to each question. In other words, the questionnaire is the best instrument that can supply the necessary information to complete a research study as it commonly used in a Behavioral science research or social research (Calderon & Gonzalez: 2005).

The self-made questionnaire is composed of three parts: The first part is about the profile of the respondents in the context of gender, age, length of service and educational qualification. While the second part is a 15 items assessment of interpersonal skills as manifested by the school administrators at Luuk NHS. And the third part is also a 12-item which entails the school administrators' supervisory skills.

Data Collection

The researchers had sought the permission from the graduate school Dean, Dr. Magna Annisa Edding Hayudini for the launching of the research questionnaire. After the approval, the researchers then sent a letter to the School Division Superintendent for Dr. Kiram Irlis, asking permission for the launching of the investigation on the subject. After which, the researchers further sent a letter to the school principal of Luuk NHS for the conduct of the study. The respondents were asked to answer the questionnaire fairly as to how they feel in the school organization as the interpersonal and supervisory skills of the school administrators. Then, the questionnaire was retrieved by the researchers a week after in a 100 percent response rate.

Statistical Tool

To analyze the gathered data, statistical tool was utilized. Meanwhile, Frequency and percentage were used to analyzed the profile of the respondents with respect to gender, age, length of service and teaching experience. Likewise, mean was utilized to determine the extent of administrator's interpersonal and supervisory skills in Luuk NHS. Also, Pearson Correlation was use to examine the relationship between administrator's interpersonal and administrator's supervisory skills. Similarly, T-test for independent sample was also used to analyze the significant difference of the perception of the respondents on the administrator's interpersonal and supervisory skills according to gender. Moreover, ANOVA was utilized to test the difference of the teachers' perceptions according to age, length of service and educational qualification.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses the school administrator's interpersonal and supervisory skills and their impact to school organizational climate of Luuk National High School S.Y 2022-2023. The school administrators include the school principal, head teachers, and all department heads of the said school. Administrator's Intrapersonal and technical skills are not included in the study.

A questionnaire validated by the panel members or experts will be the main instrument of the study. A follow up interview will also be done to clarify vague answers. Meanwhile, both descriptive and inferential statistics will be used in the study. Moreover, time constraints and cooperation from the respondents are the possible limitations of the study.

RESULTS

A. Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the results of the profile of the secondary school teachers in Luuk National High School. The following are the distributions: As to age, majority (66.7%) were male; As to age, majority (50%) were belonged to 28-35 years of age; As to length of service, majority (43.3%) have already served 16 years and above; while in terms of educational qualification, majority (63.3 %) have just finished bachelor's degree.

Table 1 : Profile of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	34	56.7
Female	26	43.3
Age		
24-27 Yrs. Old	2	3.3
28-35 Yrs. Old	30	50.0
36 Yrs. Old and beyond	28	46.7
Length of Service		
5 Yrs. and below	8	13.3
6-10 yrs.	8	13.3
11-15 yrs.	18	30.0
16 years and above	26	43.3
Educational Qualification		
Bachelor's degree	38	63.3
With master's units	16	26.7
With master's degree	2	3.3
With Doctoral units	4	6.7
With Doctoral degree	0	0.0

B. Administrators' Interpersonal Skills

Table 2 presents the interpersonal skills of the school administrators in Luuk National High School. The overall mean is 3.86 verbally described as strongly agree; while the highest specific mean is 3.97 interpreted as strongly agree and the lowest specific mean is 3.47 interpreted as Agree.

Table 2: Interpersonal skills of the administrators

Administrators' Interpersonal skills	Mean	Verbal Description
The School Administrator :		
1. Has the ability to relate with his teachers	3.90	Strongly Agree
2. Has the courage to motivate his/her teachers to go out from the comfort zones	3.80	Strongly Agree
3. Provides comfort to every teacher	3.87	Strongly Agree
4. Has truly "cares" his/her teachers at the school	3.93	Strongly Agree
5. Helps his/her teachers solve their personal problem	3.47	Agree
6. Sets out with the teachers in the school and work together	3.90	Strongly Agree
7. Ensures a win-win-situation. The principal win, (the school administrator wins, the teachers win and so as the school)	3.83	Strongly Agree
8. Provide support to teacher's professional development	3.90	Strongly Agree
9. Always believe in the capability of his/her teachers	3.90	Strongly Agree
10. Always "valued" his/her teacher in the school premises.	3.97	Strongly Agree
11. Knows how to appreciate teacher's achievements	3.93	Strongly Agree
12. Helps teachers' reach their maximum potentials	3.90	Strongly Agree
13. Listens to teachers' concern pertaining to professional and personal matters	3.83	Strongly Agree
14. Initiates connections with other schools and LGU's	3.80	Strongly Agree
15. Empowers his/her teachers by sending through continues professional trainings and development		
Overall mean	3.86	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.49- 4.00= Strongly Agree (With high extent)
 2.50- 3.50= Agree(With Moderate extent);
 1.50- 2.49 = Disagree(With lesser extent)
 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (No extent at all)

C. Administrator's Interpersonal and Profile of the Respondents

This section discusses the significant difference of the school administrator's interpersonal and supervisory skills according to respondents profile with respect to gender, age, length of service and educational qualification.

A. Administrator's Interpersonal Skills and Gender

Table 3 depicts the significant difference of administrator's interpersonal according gender. It was found that administrator's interpersonal skills have a sig. value of .081 which is above the .05 alpha level.

Table 3 : Difference according to gender

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	sig
Interpersonal Skills	male	17	3.8039	.23389	.081
	female	13	3.9231	.11815	

B. Administrator's Interpersonal Skills and Age

Table 3 presents the result for the significant difference of administrators' interpersonal skills according to age of the respondents. Data revealed that the sig. value is .05 with F value of 4.964 which found above the .05 significant level.

Table 4: Difference according to age

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Interpersonal Skills	Between Groups	.308	2	.154	4.964	.015
	Within Groups	.839	27	.031		
	Total	1.147	29			

C. Administrator's Interpersonal and Length of Service

Table 5 illustrates the significant difference in terms of interpersonal and supervisory skills of the administrators as perceived by the teachers according to their length of service. Result wise, the administrator's interpersonal skills have the sig. value of .109 and to be analyzed at .05 alpha level.

Table 5: Difference according to length of service

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Interpersonal Skills	Between Groups	.234	3	.078	2.223	.109
	Within Groups	.913	26	.035		
	Total	1.147	29			

a. Administrator's Interpersonal Skills and Teaching Experience

Table 6 presents the significant difference on the perception of the teachers on the administrator's interpersonal and administrative skills according to their teaching experience. It was found that administrator's interpersonal skill has a sig. value of .001 This is to be tested at .05 significance level.

Table 6 : Difference according to educational qualification

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Interpersonal Skills	Between Groups	.534	3	.178	7.553	.001
	Within Groups	.613	26	.024		
	Total	1.147	29			

DISCUSSION

This section discusses the profile of the school administrators of Luuk National High School and their interpersonal skills. This also incorporates how teachers perceived the administrators' interpersonal skills differ in the context of gender, age, length of service and educational qualification.

A. Profile of the Respondents

Gleaning from the Table 1, the majority or 34 (56.7%) of the teacher respondents are male; while only 26 (43.3%) are female. This implies that there are more male teachers than females at Luuk National High School. In terms of Age, 30 (50%) are belonging to the age bracket from 28-35 years old; while, 28 (46.7%) are within the age of 36 years old and above; and only two (3.3 %) are within the age category of 24-27 years old. This data suggest that the teachers are just but in their mid-range age and thereby still have the passion and motivation to teach. Meanwhile, as to the respondents length of service, the majority or 26 (43.3%) have already rendered service from 16 years and above; while 18 (30 %) of them were already in the service from 11-15 years; and only eight (13.3 %) were in the teaching profession for five years and below ; also eight (13.3 %) were also in the teaching service from 5-10 years. Moreover, in terms of their educational qualification, the majority 38 (63.3%) have only finished bachelor's degree. While only 16 (26.7 %) are still having the master's units; four (6.7%) are having their doctoral units; and two (3.3%) have completed their master's degree. This data suggest that faculty members of Luuk NHS still need to pursue graduate studies and professional advancement in the pursuit of academic standard and excellence.

The findings is supported by Abdurahman & Omar (2021) who found that The majority of teacher-respondents are in 31-40 years' age bracket, female and have been rendering services for two years and above. In addition, this is also consistent with Abdurahman N., et al. (2024) in their study on " Exploring the difficulties in teaching science among Intermediate grade teachers in selected schools in MBHTE- Sulu, Southern Philippines: Basis for program interventions who found that the majority 130 (72.2%) of the elementary school teachers were female; and majority 90 (50 %) of them were belonging to an age bracket of 36-45 years old; As to their educational qualification,

majority 110 (61.1%) have finished their bachelor's degree. While 59 (33.0%) of them were already having their masteral units.

Noticeably however, this finding is contrary with the findings of Isa J., Madjid J., et al. (2024) in their study on Administrative empowerment vis a vis school head's decision making: The case of MBHTE-Sulu, BARMM, Philippines who found that majority of the school heads in Pangutaran District, MBHTE-Sulu were male; whose age were ranged from 56-65 years old and have 31-40 years of teaching experience; While majority of them have already finished their master's degree.

B. Administrators' Interpersonal Skills

As depicted in Table 2, with an overall mean of 3.86 which is verbally interpreted as strongly agree. This means that the school administrators of Luuk NHS are performing their task relative to their interpersonal skills to a high extent. This data also points out the administrators are having excellent interpersonal skills in dealing with their subordinates.

Specifically, the teachers strongly agreed (mean = 3.97) that the school administrators always valued their teachers in the school premises . While they further strongly agreed (mean = 3.93) that school administrators have truly care their teachers; and they know also how to appreciate their teachers achievements. Meanwhile, they strongly agreed (mean=3.90) that the school administrators have the ability to relate their teachers; set out with them in the school and work together; provide supports for their personal development; and help their teachers to reach their maximum potentials.

Similarly, the teachers have strongly agreed (mean= 3.87) that the school administrators provide comfort to their teachers; while they strongly agreed too (mean = 3.83) that their administrators always ensure a win-win situation; and always listen to their concerns pertaining to professional and personal matters. Also, the teacher respondents strongly agreed (mean= 3.80) that their administrators have the courage to motivate their teachers to go out from their comfort zones ; and initiate connections with other schools and LGU's. Moreover, they agreed further (mean= 3.47) that their school administrators always help them solve their personal problems.

This finding was consistent with Asonaba and Yankyera, (2015) who found that interpersonal relation skill can be referred to as skill that the principal adopt that give room for good human interaction in the school. Basically, the tasks ahead of any school administrators are so enormous such that it requires a lot of approaches in order to “live-up-to-expectations.”

In the same context, the school leader is one of the most important individuals in the lives of teachers (Brock & Grady, 20007); therefore, the school leader is the key to teacher perceptions of feeling supported (Richards, 2005). Leaders of education need to increase their interpersonal sensitivity to prevent low staff morale and performance issues (Muse, Sperry, Voelker, Harrington, & Harris, 2003).

Furthermore, In Balla S., et al. (2024) that schools like Sulu College of Technology proves that parental support and teacher performance dimensions do not contribute much to the challenges that the school has encountered and therefore may play strong part to the development of the school performance. Hence, administrative dimension is believed to play a huge part in its academic success.

C. Administrators' Interpersonal Skills and Profile of the Respondents

This section discusses the significant difference of the administrators' interpersonal skills according to respondents' profile with respect to gender, age, length of service, and educational attainment.

c.1: Administrators Interpersonal Skills and Gender

As depicted in Table 3, there was no significant difference found in the perception of male and female teachers as to administrator's interpersonal skills as exhibited in the sig. value .555. Therefore, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference on the perception of male and female teachers on the administrators' interpersonal skills was hereby accepted. This denotes that both perceptions of the male and female teachers of Luuk NHS are almost the same.

c.2: 1: Administrators Interpersonal Skills and Age

As illustrated in Table 4. there was a significant difference found in the perception of Luuk NHS teachers as to administrator's interpersonal skills as exhibited in the sig. value .015 which is lesser than the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "there is no significant difference of the extent of interpersonal skills of the administrator" was rejected. This means that the perception of the newly hired teachers differs with those perceptions of the experienced teachers.

Along this line, administrators must realize that even though disagreement may occur, it is still possible to work with people. It would be very unusual for everyone on a staff to agree fully on every matter with the administrator, If they did, little diversity or creativity would occur resulting in the fostering of mediocrity and conformity.

c.3: 1: Administrators Interpersonal Skills and Length of Service

As illustrated in Table 5, there was no significant difference found in the perception of the teachers regardless of length of service as to administrator's interpersonal skills as exhibited in the sig. value .109. Hence, the hypothesis which states that "there is no significant difference on the administrators' interpersonal skills according to length of service" was accepted. Therefore, the perceptions of Luuk national high school teachers regardless of their length of service do not vary significantly.

c.4: 1: Administrators Interpersonal Skills and Educational Qualification

As illustrated in Table 6, there was a significant difference found in the perception of Luuk NHS teachers as to administrator's interpersonal skills as exhibited in the sig. value .015 which is lesser than the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "there is no significant difference of the extent of interpersonal skills of the administrator" is accepted. This means that the perception of those teachers who are at baccalaureate level is not the same with teachers in the masters' level.

It is believed that the key element underlying effective school administration is an administrator's ability to communicate with, understand, and influence the people with whom he comes in contact. Ability in interpersonal skills affects the implementation of the entire spectrum of administrative tasks. In order to influence change and promote a climate of cooperation and growth, an administrator must be capable of recognizing, internalizing, and applying these skills.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it can be deduced that majority of the teacher-respondents were female, 28-35 years old, with a minimum of 16 years of experience, and have a bachelor's degree. Besides, the school administrators of Luuk National High School have good interpersonal skills based on the perception of their teachers. Further, there was no significant difference found on the perception of the teachers regarding administrators' interpersonal skills in the context of gender and length of service. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. And, there was a significant difference found on the perception of the teachers regarding administrators' interpersonal skills in the context of age and educational qualification. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected.

Recommendations

- i. The school administrators should continue upgrading their interpersonal skill through professional advancement and training.
- ii. The MBHTE-BARMM may institutionalize a training program for school administrators and teachers to enhance interpersonal skills as this can be a great factor in motivating and retaining them in the teaching profession.
- iii. The MBHTE-BARMM shall require every faculty member for a continuing professional education since majority of them have only finished bachelor's degree.
- iv. The school administrators should communicate clearly their goals and strategies to their teachers through effective interpersonal skills in order to maximize school performance.
- v. Future researchers shall conduct another study of the same nature to review the major aspects of the topic and use this finding to be launching pad for further exploration.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Respecting the right of the concerned participants is at the topmost priority of the researchers. First, the researchers have sent an informed consent to the respondents which clearly explains the general objectives of the study. Besides, teachers of Luuk NHS were also informed of their rights to and not-to participate in the study. They were likewise informed that the researchers have preserved for them a maximum confidentiality. Furthermore, the data collected were actually stored in a secured archive where only the researchers can access. And, anonymization of these data was strictly observed. Moreover, all participants were treated with respect regardless of their diverse perspective and opinions. Moreover, the researchers created a safe space for the respondents to share their experiences in line with the objectives of this investigation.

Acknowledgements

The researchers are indebted to the chancellor of Mindanao State University-Sulu, Dr. Nagder J. Abdurahman for allowing the writers to undergo this research endeavor. The same recognition is due to the school administrators of Luuk NHS and faculty-respondents for the unselfish supports bestowed upon the researchers. Moreover, they wholeheartedly commend all those who in one way or the others, made this academic undertakings possible. Without them, this research would not have been made possible.

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